

VII
CUMBRE DE JEFAS Y JEFES DE ESTADO Y DE GOBIERNO
DE LA COMUNIDAD DE ESTADOS LATINOAMERICANOS Y CARIBEÑOS (CELAC)

▶ 24 de enero, 2023 | Buenos Aires

VII
CUMBRE DE JEFAS Y JEFES
DE ESTADO Y DE GOBIERNO
DE LA COMUNIDAD DE ESTADOS LATINOAMERICANOS
Y CARIBEÑOS (CELAC)

▶ 24 de enero, 2023 | Buenos Aires

LabGRIMA

Laboratory of Geopolitics, International Relations and Anisystemics Movements

OCTOBER, 2023 #07

POLICY BRIEF

BRAZIL'S RETURN TO CELAC PUTS THE COUNTRY BACK ON THE WORLD STAGE AS A LATIN AMERICAN LEADER

JÓHIDSON DE OLIVEIRA E IZAN ARAUJO

BRAZIL'S RETURN TO CELAC PUTS THE COUNTRY BACK ON THE WORLD STAGE AS A LATIN AMERICAN LEADER

What does returning to CELAC mean for Brazil? In February 2010, Mexico, the Community of Latin American and Caribbean States (CELAC), was established as a political-diplomatic discussion forum bringing together 33 Latin American countries seeking regional integration. Brazil's return to CELAC favors the country's geopolitical projection on a global scale because it removes the country from regional isolation and gives it greater bargaining power to discuss with major international players such as the European Union (EU). Let's look first at the benefits Brazil gains from breaking out of isolationism.

Brazil's return to CELAC signals the end of the country's regional isolation. Under the Bolsonaro administration, Brazil left the bloc in January 2020 because the institution gave a leading role to some undemocratic regimes in the region. Brazil's return to the bloc strengthens the regional integration process. It corrects the mistake of the previous government, which had an ideological foreign policy that isolated the country from the world. Brazil's return to the Latin American forum allows the country to be the leader in Latin America as it has the region's largest economy, population, and territory. Corroborating Ratzel's thesis that "space is power." Now that we've discussed the benefits offered to Brazil let's analyze the country's role in the discussions with the EU.

Brazil's return to CELAC will increase its bargaining power in discussions with the European Union. President Lula attended the III CELAC-EU Summit in Brussels on July 17 and 18. Discussions included environment, social inclusion, and trade between the two blocs. Latin America is important to Europeans because it has a market of 660 million inhabitants and geostrategic natural resources, as seen in the map below. In addition, Chile, Argentina, and Bolivia form the "lithium triangle" as they have 60% of the world's lithium reserves, which is essential for environmental issues and energy transition, especially now after the war in Ukraine.

We, therefore, suggest that the country's return to CELAC means a new Brazilian foreign policy paradigm, which Brazilian political geographer André Martin has called "meridionalist," aimed at securing a brasilian's prominent position among the world's major players. By leading this effort with other Latin American nations, Brazil could solidify its leadership position in the global arena.

Some might argue that CELAC puts the spotlight on regimes that don't respect democracy, institutions, and human rights. It's worth noting that individuals who believe their rights have been violated can still take action. They can turn to the OAS (Organization of American States) to file petitions with the Inter-American Commission on Human Rights. This process is similar to the European and African Human Rights Systems. CELAC plays a significant political role in the integration of Latin America and the peaceful resolution of conflicts. All these initiatives contribute to a "security community" that will resolve disputes between community members without war but through dialog, democratically.

Finally, Brazil's participation in CELAC is an excellent way of maintaining its global influence. Its return to the Latin American bloc means the end of its regional isolation and strengthens its international role in negotiations with the EU. In today's rapidly changing world, the geopolitics of power are no longer confined to Eurasia, as Mackinder said. We are now witnessing an ebb and flow to other regions of the globe, especially the Southern Hemisphere. We, therefore, suggest that the country's return to CELAC means a new Brazilian foreign policy paradigm, which Brazilian political geographer André Martin has called "meridionalist," aimed at securing a brasilian's prominent position among the world's major players. By leading this effort with other Latin American nations, Brazil could solidify its leadership position in the global arena.

About the Authors

Jóhidson de Oliveira holds a PhD in Latin American Integration from the University of São Paulo (USP), Brazil. Currently, he is an Associate Researcher at the International Institute for Geopolitics & Strategy (IIGS), USA.

Izan Araujo is PhD in Human Geography from Universidade de São Paulo (USP), Brazil. He is currently chairman of CENEGRI.

Keywords: CELAC, Regional Integration, Latin America, Geopolitics.

References

Anuário Estatístico da CEPAL, 2022, p. 13. Disponível em: <https://repositorio.cepal.org/server/api/core/bitstreams/b4e780-8395-487b-ba4f-a22412716e1b/content>. Acesso em: 10 set. 2023.

CASTRO, Ana Flavia. Após dois anos, Brasil retorna à Celac, bloco latino-americano. *Metrópoles*. DF, 06 jan. 2023. Disponível em: <https://www.metropoles.com/brasil/apos-dois-anos-brasil-retorna-a-celac-bloco-latino-americano>. Acesso em: 21 set. 2023.

Policy Briefs are produced in partnership with The International Institute for Geopolitics and Strategic Intelligence (IIGSI/USA), The Centre for Studies on Geopolitics and Foreign Affairs (CENEGRI/Brazil) and Laboratory of Geopolitics, International Relations and Antisystemic Movements (LabGRIMA/Brazil). The IIGSI and CENEGRI are independent think tanks non-profit organizations dedicated to geopolitics and international affairs research. The LabGRIMA is affiliated to the Federal University of Pelotas, Brazil.

Disclaimer

All views, positions, and conclusions expressed in this publication should be understood to be solely of the author(s).

Partner

